

Determination of Flocculation Values from Measurements of the Rate of Coagulation of an Arsenic Sulphide Sol.

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Numerous investigators have determined flocculation values from measurements of the time required for the production of a certain state of turbidity of the sol. Flocculation values thus determined are not strictly comparable as they refer to a transitory state during the process of coagulation. It is much more important to measure the velocity of coagulation as coagulation is really a process of the progressive growth of particles. Before a change in a physical property of a sol, *e.g.*, of turbidity, change in viscosity etc., can be made the basis for the determination of flocculation values, it must be clearly shown that the rate of flocculation goes parallel with changes in the physical property chosen. Gann (*Koll. Chem Beih.*, 1916, 8, 64) attempted to study the rate of coagulation of aluminium hydroxide sol by measuring the rate of change of viscosity, but his measurements are doubtful as the assumption that the rate of change of viscosity is proportional to the velocity of coagulation is not strictly valid. In the present paper an attempt has been made to determine flocculation values from measurements of the velocity or the rate of increase of turbidity of arsenious sulphide sol with different electrolytes.

During the measurements a Nutting colorimeter was adapted to function as a tyndallmeter. A 130 C.P. point-o-lite lamp is placed at S (Fig. 1). By means of a system of lenses the light was rendered parallel and was then passed through a Zeiss monochromatic filter L, which transmitted 80 per cent. of the Hg green line 5461. By means of two slits s_1 and s_2 part of the parallel beam was allowed to pass through the rectangular cell C, containing the sol-electrolyte mixture, whereas another part was allowed to fall on a right angled prism and was totally reflected.

Fig. 1.

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The intensity of the scattered beam was compared with the intensity of the beam directly reflected from the right angled prism by means of the tyndallmeter. A sample of arsenious sulphide sol was prepared by the usual method and different volumes of electrolytes were added to 1 c.c. of the sol, the total volume being made up to 4 c.c. in every case. The sol-electrolyte mixture was immediately transferred to the cell and the change in the intensity of the scattered beam with time was followed on the tyndallmeter. To eliminate the disturbing effects of the stabilising ions the electrolytes chosen were such that the negative ion was the same throughout.

Mecklenberg (*Kolloid Z.*, 1915, **16**, 97), using Odèn's sulphur sol has shown that the intensity of the scattered beam is proportional to the size of the particles of diameters between the limits $5\text{-}95\mu\mu$. Bechold and Hebler (*ibid.*, 1932, **31**, 70) using barium sulphate suspensions has shown that the above relationship is valid for particles of size up to $800\mu\mu$. In the present experiments the observations are mainly confined to the earlier stages of the process. Consequently it seems reasonable to assume that the rate of change of the intensity of the scattered beam is proportional to the rate of growth of the particles. The experimental data obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE I.

Electrolyte—HCl.

Expt. No.	Electrolyte conc.	Rate of Coagulation.			
		millinol/litre	Time min. sec.	Scale reading.	$0 \tan \theta$
I	31 25	0	18	0	
		6	0	0 1	1 02
		14	30	0 2	
II	45	2	21	0 5	
		3	56	1 3	5 08
		5	27	1 6	

TABLE I.--contd.

Electrolyte—HCl.

Expt. No.	Electrolyte conc. millimol./litre	Time		Rate of coagulation.			
		min.	sec.	Scale reading.	0	tan θ	
III	50	0	8	0	1		
		1	15	0	3		
		2	21	1	3	12	21
		4	5	1	8		
		5	6	2	0		
IV	56	2					
		0	18	0	2		
		0	51	1	0		
		1	21	1	7		
		2	9	2	1	31	60
3	21	2	4				
5	30	2	6				
V	59	37					
		0	18	0	3		
		0	36	0	6	45	1
		1	9	2	1		
2	3	2	5				
VI	62	5					
		0	21	0	6		
		0	45	1	8	56	1
1	18	2	5		48		
VII	65	62					
		0	12	0	5		
		0	21	1	9	66	2
		0	54	2	4		24
2	3	2	9				
VIII	71	94					
		0	13	1	5		
		0	30	2	5	81	6
		0	51	2	9		31
1	21	3	3				

Electrolyte—HCl.

FIG. 2.

The scale readings shown in the table represent the intensities of the scattered beams. The scale readings have been plotted against time and a series of curves have been obtained. The curve for hydrochloric acid is shown in Fig. 2 which is generally typical of the curves obtained with other monovalent electrolytes. Corresponding to hydrochloric acid concentration equal to 45 and 50 millimols per litre the curve assumes the characteristic shape of the curves for autocatalytic reactions. Similar behaviour was observed for all monovalent electrolytes. $\frac{dI}{dt}$, the rate of change of the intensity of the scattered beam with time, has been obtained in the case of each electrolyte from the above curves by the graphical method. θ , the angle between the tangent to the curve at any point and the abscissæ was read directly when the value of $\frac{dI}{dt}$ for that point was known, being equal to $\tan \theta$. The values of $\frac{dI}{dt}$ so obtained were plotted against concentration and the series of curves as shown in Figs. 3 and 4 were obtained.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

From a study of the curves (Fig. 3 and 4) which shows the variation of the rate of coagulation with change in electrolyte concentration, the flocculation values of the different electrolytes can be obtained. The values of C for different electrolytes at any fixed value of $\frac{dl}{dt}$ give the flocculation values. From the experimental

results it has been found that the flocculation values in the case of monovalent electrolytes are in the following order :—

whereas in the case of the divalent electrolytes the order is :—

The important factors during a coagulation process are the neutralisation of the charge on the particle generally by the adsorption of an oppositely charged ion and the later adsorption of one or both the ions of the coagulator by the electrically neutral aggregates formed by coalescence of discharged particles. It is evident that the difference in the orders of flocculation values obtained by different authors is caused to a large extent by the disturbances due to adsorption by flocculated aggregates. To guard against this effect in the present experiments observations have been limited to the earlier stages of coagulation.

Oden (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 311) studied the relative adsorbability of the ions using blood charcoal as the adsorbent, and in the case of the alkali metals he obtained the series :—

With the alkaline earth metals he obtained the series :—

Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 399) using arsenious sulphide precipitate as the adsorbent has also obtained the same order for both mono- and divalent ions. Since coagulation values can be taken as the inverse of adsorption values, it is interesting to note that the order of flocculation values as obtained during the present investigation is the reverse of the order for the adsorption as obtained by Oden. The present experimental arrangement thus appears to be well suited for reliable measurements of flocculation values.

Westgren (*Arkiv. kemi., Stockholm*, 1918, 7, No. 6,1) studied the slow coagulation of gold sol and from his measurements it was concluded that the order of the flocculation values changed with concentration of the coagulator. The adsorption isotherms as found by Oden (*loc. cit.*) however, do not support the above conclusion. From the present experiments it is evident that the order of flocculation

values is fixed for all different concentrations of electrolytes. Where discrepancies have been observed, they are due largely to defects in the experimental methods of determining flocculation values.

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